

Studies on Dithiocarbamates: Part XIV. Studies on 3-Phenyl-5- (*ortho*-hydroxyphenylazo)-Rhodanine as Metal Complexing Ligand (Copper complex)

P. B. Talukdar, S. Banerjee, A. K. Datta and A. Chakraborty

Preparation and properties of the titled azorhodanine have been described. The azorhodanine also forms a 1 : 1 copper-ligand complex with λ_{\max} at 535 $m\mu$ in 50% aqueous methanol (v/v). The calculated values for $\log K$ in the same medium are 5.62 and 5.71 at 25°.

Earlier we have reported^{1,2} the preparation and properties of azorhodanines (I) with various substituents on the azophenyl fragment. These compounds are usually characterised by a highly intense band in the long wave-length region. But the presence of a *ortho*-phenolic group in I ($R_1 = OH$) is of particular interest since structurally similar phenolic azo-dyes are well known³ for their propensity to form organo-metallic complexes which are known to play a vital role in biological phenomenon. Besides this, azo dyestuffs containing heterocyclic ring systems have been studied to a lesser extent^{4,5}.

In this report, we, therefore, describe the preparation and the properties of 3-phenyl-5-(*o*-hydroxyphenylazo)-rhodanine and the characteristics of the copper complex formed by the same as a ligand.

E X P E R I M E N T A L

Spectrophotometric measurements were made in Hilger UVISPEC spectrophotometer in 1 cm cells. pH measurements were carried out with a standard Cambridge pH meter.

Standard solution of copper was prepared by dissolving a weighed quantity of copper sulphate (G.R.E.M.) in double distilled water ($4.740 \times 10^{-4} M$) and the aliquots were diluted to obtain 2.370×10^{-4} and 1.185×10^{-4} molar solutions.

A stock solution ($1.185 \times 10^{-4} M$) of the ligand (L) was prepared in methanol (B.D.H., acetone-free) from pure crystals obtained by the following lit.¹ method.

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3. H. Zollinger, *Azo and Diazo Chemistry*, Interscience Publishers, New York, 1961, p. 338.
4. R. G. Anderson and G. Nickless, *Anal. Chim. Acta*, 1967, **39**, 469.
5. R. G. Anderson and G. Nickless, *Analyst*, 1968, **93**, 13, 20.

An ice-cold solution of the *o*-aminophenol in dil.HCl was diazotised and added with stirring to an ice-cold solution of 3-phenyl rhodanine in DMF-acetone mixture in the presence of excess sodium acetate. The precipitated solid was worked up in the usual way and repeatedly crystallised from ethanol-acetone mixture to furnish (65% yield) thin red needles, m.p. (depends on the rate of heating), 237–39°, dec. λ_{\max} (methanol) at 225.0 (15,570), \sim 258 sh, 266.0 (14,520), 274 (14,520), \sim 303 (9.400, wide) and 447 $m\mu$ (27,900). Found : N = 12.65; $C_{15}H_{11}N_3O_2S_2$ requires N, 12.76%.

Isobestic point and apparent pK_a values of the ligand : In 50% methanol-buffer solutions (v/v , $\mu = 0.05$) the ligand was found to exhibit several isobestic points at 457, 372, 332 and 296 $m\mu$. At the same time, the long-wave length band at 447 $m\mu$ shifts to the red at 490 $m\mu$ under alkaline condition. But the striking feature is the appearance of a band at 362 $m\mu$ while the other band positions in the UV region remain practically unaffected under alkaline condition. In contrast to this observation, the band positions in other *ortho*-substituted (Cl, Br and MeO)-azorhodanines⁶ around 300 $m\mu$ region remain unaffected in the presence of alkali.

In accordance with the above observation, spectrophotometric titrations⁷ at 365 $m\mu$ in methanol-buffer mixture (1 : 1, v/v , $\mu = 0.05$) gave an apparent pK_a of 6.25 due to the phenolic group. This is undoubtedly low compared to the usual pK_a value (\sim 8 to 10) of structurally similar azo-compounds^{3,4,5}. One way of explaining this is to assume relatively strong basicity of the β -N-(resonance effect) resulting in fairly developed bonding between phenolic proton and β -N⁸. If this is reasonable, then complexation is likely to be slow and weak⁵.

The apparent pK_a (7.45) due to the active hydrogen at C₅ in the rhodanine ring was also determined in methanol-buffer mixture (1 : 1, v/v , $\mu = 0.05$) by spectrophotometric technique² at 500 $m\mu$ (Henderson-Hasselbalch equation). However, the absorbance values were corrected to zero-time readings as the ligand tends to decompose under the alkaline condition. The calculated value is well within the range found earlier for similar compounds².

As explained below, complexation between the ligand and the metal solution was always run in 50% aqueous methanol (v/v) in absence of any added electrolyte. All the experiments were run at 25–26°.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Absorbance curve : When the methanolic solution of the ligand (L) was added to an aqueous solution of the metal (M), the mixture slowly turned purple with concomitant fall in pH. Examination of solutions containing M/L in different mole ratios (1 : 1 to 1 : 4) against a similarly prepared reagent blank offered a family of curves with a single peak at 535 $m\mu$. As the ligand shows negligible absorption around 535 $m\mu$, the band position

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8. H. H. Freedman, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1961, 83, 2900;

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remains practically unaffected when the spectra were redrawn against 50% aqueous methanol as blank. It therefore suggests the formation of a single complex in solution⁹ and subsequent observations are based on absorbance values recorded at 535 $m\mu$ against 50% aqueous methanol (v/v).

Effect of pH and stability of the complex : Identical solutions containing known amounts of the ligand and the metal were adjusted to different pH values with acetate buffers or 0.01 *M* NaOH and their follow up shows that maximum absorbance could be obtained only in the pH range 5 to 7. However, colour formation is faster on the higher side of pH and considerably slower on the lower side of pH to the extent that maximum absorbance was not attained in some cases even after 24 hrs. But the complex is only moderately stable in the sense that there was regular fall off in maximum absorbance depending on the pH of the medium; higher the pH, faster is the fall off in absorbance. Since a plain mixture of the ligand and the metal in several mole ratios in aqueous methanol gave an effective pH of about 5.1, subsequent studies were conducted without adjustment of pH.

Stoichiometry of the complex : The composition of the complex was ascertained by Job's method of continued variation¹⁰. For this purpose, maximum absorbance values for a series of solutions with different M/(M+L) ratios (varied from 0 to 1.0 at intervals of 0.1) were determined against a similarly prepared blank with methanol and water, and their plots exhibited sharp peak at 0.5 mole fraction only, indicating 1 : 1 metal-ligand composition of the complex (Fig. 1).

Fig. 1

The stoichiometry of the complex was further verified by the mole ratio method¹¹ with clean breaks at 1 : 1 mole ratio as shown in Fig. 2,

Fig. 2

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On the basis of the above results structure II may be tentatively assigned to the complex and this is in line with similar organometallic complexes of *ortho*-hydroxyaryl azo compounds³.

Evaluation of the stability constant : Since the complex formation of the given system can be expressed by

the stability constant (K) of the complex for pairs of mixture with identical absorbance values is given by

$$K = \frac{X}{(a_1 - X)(b_1 - X)} = \frac{X}{(a_2 - X)(b_2 - X)}$$

where X is the equilibrium concentration of the complex, a_1 and a_2 and the initial concentrations of the metal, b_1 and b_2 are the initial concentrations of the ligand. Solving for X , it is now possible to estimate¹² the magnitude of the K . It was also estimated from the mole ratio curve from the calculated degree of dissociation (α). The values obtained by these methods were in close agreement and the calculated values for $\log K$ were found to be 5.62 and 5.7 giving a mean value of 5.66. The free energy of formation of the complex was determined from the relationship, $\Delta G = -RT \ln K = -7.75$ Kcal/mole, corresponding to the mean value of $\log K$. The observed ϵ_{max} is around 20,000.

Our thanks are due to Sri P. Bagehi, Research Director, for his keen interest in our work.

Research and Development Division,
East India Pharmaceutical Works Ltd.,
Calcutta-61.

Received November 10, 1970

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